

BEYOND BUDGETING PRACTICES AND SUSTAINABLE ORGANISATIONAL GROWTH IN NIGERIA: ROLE OF DIGITAL MATURITY

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Abstract: *The study examined the effect of beyond budgeting practices on sustainable organizational growth of listed firms in Nigeria, with emphasis on the moderating role of digital maturity. The study was grounded on the theory of contingency. A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The population comprised 154 listed firms, while Taro Yamene method was used to determine the sample size. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires after validity and reliability tests. The questionnaire responses were analysed using univariate, bivariate and multivariate techniques. The findings revealed a positive and statistically significant relationships between degree of decentralization, benchmark-based targets, adoptive planning systems, dynamic funding systems, performance-based incentives, and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The study also found that digital maturity positively and significantly moderates the connection between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable organizational growth. This study contributes to knowledge by extending beyond budgeting literature within the Nigerian context through empirical evidence that degree of decentralization, benchmark-based targets, adoptive planning systems, dynamic funding systems, performance-based incentives significantly enhance financial sustainability of listed firms. Also, the study enriches existing literature through the application of quantitative cross-sectional analysis in investigating adaptive management practices and organizational sustainability in an emerging economy context. The study concludes that adaptive management practices and digital capabilities are critical to enhancing financial sustainability and long-term organizational growth among listed firms in Nigeria.*

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Introduction

In a period of increasing industrial expansion and intensifying pressures, conventional budgeting systems have progressively been criticised for their rigour, lack of approachability, and failure to support organisational responsiveness. To address these restrictions, several organisations around the world have adopted Beyond Budgeting Practices (BBP) as a budgeting approach that replaces static annual budgets with adaptive, decentralised, and performance-oriented management processes that encourage flexibility, real-time decision-making, and employee empowerment. Hope and Fraser (2003) stressed that conventional budgeting practices have long been criticised for being stiff, time-consuming, and uneven in the contemporary dynamic business environment. Conventional annual budgets often constrain managerial flexibility, discourage innovation, and promote short-term performance orientation rather than long-term value creation (Alhalawi & Dammak, 2024). In reaction to these limitations, the concept of Beyond Budgeting arose as a management belief that promotes decentralised decision-making, adaptive planning, rolling forecasts, and relative performance evaluation (Bogsnes, 2009). Rather than having confidence in fixed annual targets, beyond budgeting practices (BBP)

emphasise responsiveness, openness, and continuous development.

The central idea of beyond budgeting accentuates continuous planning, rolling estimates, and decentralised responsibility rather than fixed, top-down financial goals. According to Schmidt (2024), beyond budgeting permits corporations to change conventional annual budgets with continuous forecasting and adaptive planning. Beyond budgeting, let's managers make decisions in real time rather than relying on fixed annual targets (Schmidt, 2024). Beyond budgeting practices, which include rolling forecasts, decentralised decision-making, and relative performance evaluation, have been widely promoted as alternatives to traditional budgeting (Alhalawi & Dammak, 2024). Schmidt (2024) argues that by focusing on decentralisation, elasticity and modification, Beyond Budgeting confronts the conventional approaches to budget preparation and presentation. The author further maintains that it specifies a modification from conventional budgeting procedures that may not be appropriate for the contemporary changing corporate environment. Consequently, Beyond Budgeting supports a more flexible and adaptive budgeting approach, helping firms to properly manage their financial resources and better adjust to a changing business environment. Research suggests that organisations adopting beyond budgeting principles can improve responsiveness, strategic flexibility, and general performance (Bourmistrov & Kaarbøe, 2013).

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Conversely, the success of beyond-budget implementation differs across organisations, can be influenced significantly by internal contextual factors. One such factor is digital maturity. Digital maturity refers to the extent to which an organisation effectively integrates digital technologies into its operations, strategy, and culture (Kane et al., 2015). Organisations with high digital maturity leverage data analytics, real-time information systems, automation, and integrated digital platforms to improve decision-making and performance management processes. Since beyond budgeting relies heavily on timely information, decentralised control, and adaptive forecasting, digital maturity may strengthen the effectiveness of these practices (Bogsnes, 2009; Kane et al., 2015). Firms with advanced digital capabilities are more likely to support continuous planning and real-time performance monitoring, thereby enhancing sustainable organisational growth. A further important contextual variable is organisational culture, defined as the shared values, norms, and beliefs that guide behaviour within an organisation (Schein, 2010). A culture that promotes empowerment, transparency, collaboration, and innovation aligns closely with the principles of beyond budgeting. Conversely, hierarchical and control-oriented cultures may resist decentralisation and flexibility, undermining the effectiveness of BBP. According to contingency theory, management control systems are more effective when aligned with

organisational and environmental contexts (Otley, 2016). Therefore, organisational culture may act as a moderating factor in the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and organisational outcomes. Sustainable organisational growth expands beyond short-term financial performance to include long-term economic, social, and strategic sustainability (Eccles et al, 2014). Sustainable growth requires adaptability, innovation, efficient resource utilisation, and strategic alignment – elements that beyond budgeting aims to enhance. However, in emerging economies such as Nigeria, firms operate within environments characterised by economic volatility, infrastructural challenges, regulatory uncertainty, and increasing competitive pressures. Listed firms in Nigeria must continuously adapt to fluctuating exchange rates, policy reforms, and technological disruptions to remain competitive and sustainable. Despite growing global interest in beyond budgeting and digital transformation, empirical research examining their combined effects in emerging markets remains limited. Furthermore, few studies have simultaneously investigated how digital maturity and organisational culture moderate the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable organisational growth. Given Nigeria's evolving corporate landscape and increasing emphasis on digital transformation among listed firms, understanding these moderating mechanisms is

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both theoretically and practically significant. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the moderating role of digital maturity in the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable organisational growth of listed firms in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the moderating effects of digital maturity on the relationship between beyond-budgeting practices and sustainable organisational growth among listed firms in Nigeria. The following specific objectives were analysed in this study:

1. To investigate the effect of the degree of decentralisation on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.
2. To assess the effect of benchmark-based targets on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.
3. To evaluate the effect of the adaptive planning system on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.
4. To determine whether the dynamic funding system improves the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.
5. To investigate the effect of the performance-based incentives on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.
6. To evaluate whether digital maturity moderates the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable growth of listed firms in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were analysed in this study:

1. What is the relationship between the degree of decentralisation and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria?
2. How does benchmark-based targets affect the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria?
3. Does the adaptive planning system contribute to the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria?
4. What is the relationship between the dynamic funding system and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria?
5. How does the performance-based incentives affect the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria?
6. Does digital maturity moderate the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable growth of listed firms in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The study tested the following research hypotheses:

Ho₁: Degree of decentralisation has no significant effect on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Benchmark-based targets have no significant effect on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.

Ho₃: The adaptive planning system has no significant effect on the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.

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Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between the dynamic funding system and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.

Ho₅: There is no significant relationship between performance-based incentives and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria.

Ho₆: Digital maturity does not significantly moderate the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable growth of listed firms in Nigeria.

Justification of the Study

The justification for this study is anchored on theoretical, empirical, methodological, contextual, and practical grounds. This study contributes to the advancement of management accounting and organisational theory by integrating Resource-based Theory with Contingency Theory. While beyond budgeting provides a framework for adaptive and decentralised management control systems (Hope & Fraser, 2003; Bogsnes, 2009), contingency theory posits that the effectiveness of such systems depends on contextual variables (Otley, 2016). Although prior studies suggest that beyond budgeting enhances organisational performance (Bourmistrov & Kaarbøe, 2013), empirical evidence linking it to sustainable organisational growth remains limited, particularly in emerging economies. Most existing research focuses on developed countries, leaving a geographical and contextual gap in literature. Nigeria, as one of Africa's largest economies, presents a unique business environment characterised by economic

volatility, regulatory complexity, infrastructural challenges, and accelerating digital transformation. Empirical findings from developed economies cannot be automatically generalised to Nigerian listed firms due to differences in institutional structures, governance systems, and technological readiness. This study is therefore justified in providing context-specific empirical evidence on the effectiveness of beyond budgeting practices within Nigerian publicly listed firms. From a managerial perspective, organisations are increasingly investing in digital transformation initiatives and management control reforms without clear empirical guidance on how these factors interact. Beyond budgeting requires decentralised authority, real-time information systems, and adaptive performance monitoring. However, without adequate digital maturity and a supportive organisational culture, implementation may fail. By examining how digital maturity and organisational culture moderate the relationship between beyond budgeting and sustainable growth, this study provides practical insights to: Corporate executives and CFOs seeking to modernise budgeting systems, Boards of directors concerned with long-term sustainability, Policymakers promoting corporate governance reforms, Investors evaluating organisational resilience and adaptability. The findings will help managers understand not just whether to adopt beyond budgeting, but under what organisational conditions it yields optimal

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results. Many prior studies examine direct relationships between management control systems and performance outcomes. However, organisational realities are rarely linear. This study adopts a moderating framework that captures interaction effects, offering a more nuanced understanding of organisational performance dynamics. By simultaneously examining digital maturity and organisational culture as moderators, the study introduces a multidimensional analytical approach that enhances methodological rigour and explanatory power. Listed firms in Nigeria operate under the oversight of regulatory bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). These firms are expected to demonstrate transparency, accountability, and sustainable value creation. Understanding how

innovative budgeting practices contribute to sustainable growth supports policy initiatives aimed at strengthening corporate governance, financial transparency, and long-term economic development. The study's findings may therefore inform regulatory recommendations and corporate best practices. Sustainable organisational growth contributes to employment generation, shareholder wealth creation, economic stability, and national development. In a developing economy like Nigeria, improving organisational resilience and adaptability has broader macroeconomic implications. By identifying management practices and contextual capabilities that promote sustainable growth, this study indirectly contributes to national economic sustainability and competitiveness.

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Literature Review
Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Authors Creation

Concept of Beyond Budgeting Model: Beyond budgeting has been suggested as another reasonable accounting and finance model that facilitates corporations to manage performance in dynamic business environments (Hope and Fraser, 2003). The substance of beyond budgeting is to migrate from traditional

budgeting principles by focusing on relative improvement rather than fixed performance contracts and shifting from top-down control to bottom-up empowerment. Instead of adopting rigid measures and incentives, beyond budgeting focuses on providing power to front-line teams. Thus, this concept is deemed to allow companies to adapt their strategies quickly to changing market requirements. By

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empowering lower-level managers, the beyond budgeting concept aims to enable companies to maintain close relationships with customers (Hope and Fraser, 2001). Hoper and Fraser (2001) further propose that the concept also allows companies to attract and keep talented employees by providing a challenging work environment. In this vein, proponents of the beyond budgeting approach suggest that the performance of employees should be evaluated at the end of each year and that the evaluation should be based on the results that employees could have achieved under the given circumstances of that period. Beyond budgeting practices, which include rolling forecasts, decentralised decision-making, and relative performance evaluation, have been widely promoted as alternatives to traditional budgeting (Alhalawi & Dammak, 2024). Alhalawi and Dammak, (2024) maintain that the Beyond Budgeting Principles, as defined in the Beyond Budgeting White Paper, emphasize objectives based on continuous relative progress, rewarding relative performance in the future, ongoing planning, resource allocation based on need, companywide coordination, and the use of key performance indicators (KPIs), relative indicators and trends for control. Beyond Budgeting Leadership Principles focus on governance based on principles and limits, fostering an environment that rewards relative achievement, empowering front-line staff with decision-making authority, creating a network of small units responsible for outcomes, shifting

attention to improving customer results and promoting open and shared communication. The BBP rests on numerous principles, such as decentralised decision-making: Responsibility for decisions is pushed to managers and teams closer to operations, allowing faster, context-sensitive responses (Alhalawi & Dammak, 2022), relative performance evaluation: Instead of rigid fixed targets, performance is measured against external benchmarks or peer units, promoting continuous improvement, rolling forecasts and Continuous Planning: Annual budgets are replaced by dynamic forecasts and flexible resource allocation that reflect real-time business conditions (Batt, 2025), adaptive Leadership and Organisational Culture: The model requires a culture of trust, transparency, and empowerment, where employees are encouraged to make decisions and innovate. Studies show that the adoption of the BBP improves organisational agility, strategic alignment, and sustainable growth, particularly when combined with a supportive organisational culture and digital maturity (Uche & Abiodun, 2025; Alhalawi & Dammak, 2022). It is increasingly applied in both developed and developing countries, including Nigeria, demonstrating its relevance in dynamic business environments where traditional budgeting approaches are often insufficient.

Concept of Sustainable Organisational Growth: Sustainable organisational growth refers to the ability of an organisation to expand its operations, increase profitability, and

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improve performance over time while maintaining social, environmental, and economic responsibilities. Unlike mere short-term growth, sustainable growth emphasises long-term value creation, resilience, and the alignment of organisational practices with broader societal and environmental goals (Bindeeba, et al, 2025; Barreto et al, 2025). According to Bindeeba et al. (2025), sustainable organisational growth requires balancing financial performance with environmental and social responsibilities. Sustainable growth can be achieved through adaptive strategies, digital maturity, and innovation (Barreto et al., 2025; Vrontis et al., 2024). Organisations adopting beyond budgeting and digital transformation are more likely to achieve long-term sustainable growth (Uche & Abiodun, 2025; Bindeeba et al., 2025). The key elements of sustainable organisational growth are balanced economic performance: generating profits without compromising long-term organisational health or stakeholder interests; innovation and Adaptability: Continuously innovating products, services, and processes to remain competitive in dynamic markets; environmental and social responsibility: Integrating corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainable practices into the organisational strategy; and capability development: Strengthening human capital, digital infrastructure, and organisational culture to support growth (Vrontis et al, 2024). Sustainable growth is particularly important in emerging economies, such as Nigeria, where

organisations face volatile markets, regulatory challenges, and technological disruption. Research indicates that practices like beyond budgeting, digital transformation, and supportive organisational culture significantly contribute to sustainable growth by enhancing agility, resource efficiency, and long-term competitiveness (Bindeeba et al., 2025; Uche & Abiodun, 2025).

Concept of Digital Maturity: Digital maturity refers to the extent to which an organisation has adopted, integrated, and optimised digital technologies, processes, and capabilities to achieve strategic objectives, improve operational efficiency, and enhance decision-making. It reflects not only the level of technological adoption but also the organisation's cultural readiness, organisational structure, and ability to leverage digital tools for innovation and sustainable growth (Peixoto et al, 2026; Ramadan et al., 2023). According to Peixoto et al. (2026), digital maturity reflects an organisation's ability to integrate technology, processes, and culture to achieve strategic objectives. Digital maturity enables firms to implement flexible management practices and improve decision-making (Ramadan et al., 2023; Vrontis et al., 2024). Organisations with higher digital maturity are better positioned to adopt Beyond Budgeting practices and achieve sustainable growth (Bindeeba et al., 2025; Uche & Abiodun, 2025). An organisation with high digital maturity can seamlessly integrate digital technologies across business functions, make

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data-driven decisions, innovate rapidly, and respond effectively to market changes. Conversely, low digital maturity indicates limited digital capability, fragmented processes, and a reliance on traditional management approaches (Uche & Abiodun, 2025). Digital maturity is particularly important in organisations adopting Beyond Budgeting Practices, as it enables real-time planning, rolling forecasts, and adaptive performance management. Studies indicate that organisations with higher digital maturity are more likely to successfully implement adaptable management models and achieve sustainable organisational growth (Bindeeba et al, 2025; Uche & Abiodun, 2025). Digital maturity consists of key dimensions such as the adoption of modern digital tools and systems across processes; optimisation of workflows and operations through digital solutions; using analytics and business intelligence for strategic choices; developing organisational culture and leadership that supports innovation, flexibility, and digital adoption; and leveraging digital capabilities to enhance customer experience and market responsiveness (Peixoto et al., 2026; Vrontis et al, 2024).

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on contingency theory, which provides a robust theoretical lens for examining the connection between beyond budgeting practices and organizational growth in Nigeria. This theory argues that there is no

single best way to lead an organization. Instead, the most effective leadership or organizational structure depends on internal and external situational factors such as environment, technology, size structure, etc. The major advocates of contingency theory include Fred Fiedler, Paul Lawrence and Jay Lorsch, Joan Woodward, Tom Burns, G. M. Stalker Henry Mintzberg and Alfred D. Chandler Jr. The theory argues that organizational effectiveness does not result from the application of universal management principles but from the alignment between organizational systems and contextual variables. In the context of budgeting, contingency theory suggests that the appropriateness and effectiveness of any control mechanism depend on situational factors. Given the increasing volatility of Nigeria's economic and regulatory environment, rigid conventional budgeting systems may no longer provide the flexibility required for sustainable growth. Beyond budgeting practices, which emphasise adaptive planning, decentralized decision-making, and continuous performance evaluation, may therefore offer a better contextual fit. This theoretical framework explains how contingency theory underpins the link between beyond budgeting practices and organizational growth. Contingency theory predicts that the stronger the alignment between beyond budgeting practices and contextual factors, the greater the likelihood of improved organizational growth. This theory is appropriate for this study, which explains

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variations in management control effectiveness across contexts, provides a structural lens for analysing budgeting systems in dynamic environments and supports the argument that beyond budgeting effectiveness depends on situational fit rather than universal superiority. According to contingency theory, the effectiveness of management control systems, such as BBP, depends on their alignment with organisational conditions, such as technology and culture (Aliu, 2025). Contingency theory posits that there is no universally optimal management system; instead, performance outcomes are contingent on situational factors such as technology, environment, and structure (Aliu, 2025; Hammouch et al., 2024). Digital maturity and organisational culture are contingency factors that influence how BBM contributes to sustainable organisational growth (Aliu, 2025; Piosik & Karmańska, 2023). Applying Contingency Theory to this study, the adoption of BBP is expected to enhance sustainable organisational growth, but its success depends on the moderating effects of digital maturity and organisational culture. Organisations with high digital maturity and supportive cultures are better equipped to implement BBP practices effectively, achieve flexibility, and respond to dynamic environmental demands. Conversely, organisations with low digital maturity or rigid cultures may struggle to reap the benefits of BBP, highlighting the contingency-based nature of managerial effectiveness. Contingency

Theory provides a robust theoretical lens for understanding the conditions under which BBP can contribute to sustainable organisational growth. It underscores the importance of contextual alignment, making it particularly relevant for examining the moderating roles of digital maturity and organisational culture in the relationship between BBP and organisational performance.

Empirical Review

Mahohoma and Boschetti (2025) conducted an empirical study examining the impact of BBP and financial performance within the South African non-ferrous metal industry. Their research provides evidence on how adaptive budgeting systems influence organizational outcomes in a dynamic industrial environment. The study employed a quantitative research design based on secondary financial data analysis. The study focused on non – ferrous metal firms in South Africa for 60 months (2020 – 2024), and financial statements of sampled firms were used as the major source of data collection, while paired sample t-tests were used for data analysis. The study revealed that firms that adopted BBP experienced improved revenue outcomes, suggesting that flexible budgeting systems assist organisations in responding more effectively to market changes. The findings also provided that despite increased revenue performance, BBP did not significantly improve operating levels, largely due to increasing cost variability in the industry. The authors concluded that BBP should be

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combined with effective cost control and real - time financial sustainability.

Alhalawi and Dammak (2024) investigated beyond budgeting as an alternative to traditional budgeting in Iraqi SMEs, focusing on how BBP impact on financial performance, non-financial performance and competitive advantage. The study adopted a sample of 353 accountants from Iraqi SMEs drawn from a large population of 22,974. The study used a quantitative survey design using primary data collected from structured questionnaires. The questionnaire was validated using factor loadings, reliability and construct validity verified with maximum likelihood estimation and the responses from the questionnaire were analysed using structural equation modelling and multiple regression via SPSS and AMOS 26. The findings of the study revealed that BBP was found to positively and significantly impact financial performance measures. Also, BBP explained about 12% of the variation in financial performance in the regression model. The study also indicated that adopting BBP leads to better budgeting processes, improved resource allocation, and sound financial management, which are essential for sustainable revenue growth and financial resilience. Furthermore, BBP had a significant positive impact on non-financial performance, explaining about 16% of the variation and a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage via differentiation.

Valdiansyah and Augustine (2021) studied how BBP, along with competitor accounting and transparency, influences competitive advantage and organizational performance in Indonesian SMEs. The authors used quantitative survey design and structural equation modelling to test direct and mediated connections. A sample of 155 respondents (business owners, financial managers/supervisors from SMEs located in six Indonesian islands. Data was collected using online questionnaires, including Likert-scale items measuring BBP, competitor accounting, transparency, competitive advantage, and organizational performance. The analysis of data was achieved using SEM via SMART PLS. The study found that BBP positively influence competitive advantage in Indonesian SMEs. This suggests that when firms adopt BBP, they are more likely to achieve strategic positioning in the market. Also, BBP did not have a statistically significant direct effect on overall organizational performance in the sample and competitive advantage functions as a process through which BBP creates value for SMEs.

Schmitz et al (2019) analysed BBP and organisational justice perceptions with organisations in German cooperative banks. The study employed a quantitative research design to investigate the relationship between BBP and organisational justice perceptions. The study adopted a survey-based empirical approach, which enabled the authors to collect primary data from employees regarding their experiences with management control systems

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and organisational justice. A total of 990 participants filled out the questionnaire, and 738 were retained for the study. The researchers collected data using a structured questionnaire survey. The survey included a Likert-scale question, where respondents indicated their level of agreement with statements about management practices and fairness within their organisations. The study used Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS – SEM) as the primary statistical analysis technique. The researchers evaluated the reliability and validity using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, while the validity of the constructs was evaluated through convergent and discriminant validity. After confirming the reliability and validity of the measurement model, the authors tested the structural relationships between BBP and organisational justice. The results indicated that several beyond-budgeting characteristics had statistically significant positive effects on both informational and interpersonal justice. The statistical results confirm that decentralisation, transparency, enhance employees' perceptions of fairness in organisational decision-making processes. Consequently, BBP can serve as an effective management control approach that improves both organisational culture and employee associations. These results suggest that organisations implementing beyond budgeting principles may create fairer and more transparent organisational environments.

He and Ismail (2023) empirically investigated the link between staff capacity and performance-based budgeting (PBB) and their impact on organizational performance in Chinese public universities. The study adopted quantitative research design using survey methods to examine the connections among the study variables. The research focused on Chinese public universities. A purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents involved in financial management and budgeting activities. A sample size of 271 participants completed an online questionnaire survey. The study used a multi-method statistical approach including Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS – SEM), Process Macro and Necessary Condition Analysis (NCA), these analytical tools enabled the researchers to examine direct, indirect (mediating), and moderating effects among the variables. The findings show that performance-based budgeting enhances accountability and resource allocation, leading to better institutional outcomes. The interaction between staff capacity and budgeting practices further strengthens performance, indicating that budgeting reforms are more effective when employees possess adequate professional skills. The study concludes that universities and public sector institutions should invest in capacity building and adopt performance-oriented budgeting frameworks to achieve improved organizational performance.

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Msiza et al (2023) analysed the role of beyond budgeting and rolling forecasts in improving management in public schools. The study adopted a quantitative survey research design to examine the connection between BBP, RFP and management improvement in public schools. The study focused on public schools in the Cape Town Metropolitan area of South Africa. A sample of 100 public schools was selected for the study. Data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to school administrators and management staff responsible for financial management. The researchers used statistical tools including reliability and validity tests, discriminate validity analysis, partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS – SEM) and SPSS for data processing and analysis. The study revealed that BBP positively influences management effectiveness, RFP enhances financial planning and monitoring, the integration of flexible budgeting tools improves financial management in public schools, and training school administrators in modern financial management tools can improve institutional performance. The study concluded that flexible budgeting tools enhance financial planning, accountability, and managerial effectiveness in educational institutions and recommended that educational authorities provide training on modern budgeting techniques.

Handayani et al (2024) investigated the challenges and effectiveness of performance-

based budgeting (PBB) in Indonesian private higher education institutions. The study focused particularly on how budget limitations affect the implementation and effectiveness of performance – based budgeting systems. The study adopted a quantitative research design to examine the connection among variables. The population consisted of private higher education institutions in Indonesia. Respondents were heads of financial management departments in these institutions. A total of 213 universities participated in the survey. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire combined with open-ended questions to obtain information about the implementation of performance-based budgeting. The study used quantitative statistical analysis to examine the effect of budget limitations on performance-based budgeting dimensions such as performance orientation, implementation flexibility, and functional budgeting approach. The study revealed that budget limitations significantly hinder the implementation of performance-based budgeting, financial constraints reduce the flexibility and effectiveness of budgeting systems, organizational culture and leadership also influence the success of budgeting and institutions should improve financial planning and adopt strategies to mitigate budget limitations.

Pribadi and Biduri (2024) analysed how budget participation and budget target clarity influence organizational performance in regional government agencies in Indonesia. The study

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focused on regional apparatus organisations (OPDs) in Sidoarjo regency and explored whether organizational commitment moderates the link between budgeting practices and organizational performance. The study adopted a quantitative research design to examine the link between budgeting variables and organizational performance. The population consisted of regional apparatus organizations (OPDs) in Sidoarjo regency, Indonesia. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents. Data were collected from 78 respondents across 26 government agencies. The study used partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS – SEM). Analysis was conducted using Smart PLS version 3.0 to test the connection between variables. The findings revealed that budget participation significantly improves organizational performance, budget target clarity has a significantly positive effect on performance, organizational commitment strengthens the link between budget target clarity and organizational performance, and clear budgeting systems and employee participation enhance performance in public sector organisations.

Soatov (2025) investigated the applicability and impact of BBP in Uzbekistan’s banking sector. The study focusses on how moving beyond traditional budgeting characteristics by rigid annual plans and centralized controls can contribute to adaptive financial management in a dynamic economic environment. The study adopted qualitative and interpretative empirical

analysis grounded in case studies, literature synthesis, and application of BBP to banking sector. The study applied exploratory empirical analysis as research design and secondary qualitative data collected from Svenska, Handelsbanken, UBS banking sector reports and performance metrics with analysis of budgeting processes and performance outcomes. The study concludes that beyond budgeting enhances adaptability in dynamic banking environments, rolling forecasts and decentralized decision – making supports quicker responses to market changes, and investment in digital analytics and performance systems facilitates successful adoption. Consequently, the findings suggest that BBP can improve financial performance and competitive agility in emerging market banking sector.

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design using a cross – sectional survey approach. A quantitative design is appropriate because it enables the researcher to measure the strength and direction of association among variables (beyond budgeting practices, digital maturity, organizational culture and sustainable organizational growth) and to generalize findings across the study population. The study also employs an exploratory research design to test the causal connections among the variables and determine whether digital maturity and organizational culture moderate the link between BBP and sustainable organizational growth. The population of the study comprises

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all listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). As of December 2025, there are 156 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. The study focused on senior management staff for these firms, particularly those involved in finance, accounting, strategy, budgeting, digital transformation, and corporate planning, because they are more knowledgeable about budgeting practices, and digital initiatives. The sample size was derived using Taro Yamene (1967) formula and the sample size is approximately 112 listed firms. The study also employed stratified random sampling to ensure representation of firms across different sectors such as financial services, consumer goods, industrial goods, oil and gas, ICT, and healthcare. Within each firm, (112 x 5) 560 respondents were selected using purposive sample, focusing on managers and executives involved in budgeting and strategic decision making. The study used primary data, and the data was obtained through a structured questionnaire administered to selected respondents in the sampled listed firms. The study used a structured questionnaire divided into demographics characteristics, beyond budgeting practices adoption and use, digital maturity practices, organizational culture behaviors and perceptions of sustainable organizational growth. The questionnaire contains closed – ended questions measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly Disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4) and strongly agree (5). The study employed

beyond budgeting practices (BBP) (degree of decentralization, benchmark-based targets, adaptive planning system, dynamic funding system and performance-based incentives) as an independent variable adapted from Alhalawi & Dammak (2024). Sustainable organizational growth (financial sustainability and social sustainability) as dependent variable adapted from Ariyibi et al (2025), Nogueira et al (2024). Digital maturity (digital infrastructure capability, data driven decision making, automation of financial processes, integration of digital technologies) were used as moderator variables adopted from Yang (2025), Guller and Tosinoglu (2025), and Carroll and Gaitan (2025), Etuk and Adebayo (2025). The questionnaire adopts content and face validity. Experts in accounting, management, and research methodology reviewed the instrument to ensure that the questions adequately measure the constructs of the study. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.70 or above, which was considered acceptable, indicating that the instrument is reliable. Data obtained from the questionnaire administered were analysed using statistical software and descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multiple regression and structural equation model (SEM) was applied to test the overall research model. The multiple regression was guided by a linear model below:

$$FIS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DOD + \beta_2 BBT + \beta_3 APS + \beta_4 DFS + \beta_5 PBI + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

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$$FIS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DOD + \beta_2 BBT + \beta_3 APS + \beta_4 DFS + \beta_5 PBI + \beta_6 DGM + \beta_7 (DOD * DGM) + \beta_8 (BBT * DGM) + \beta_9 (APS * DGM) + \beta_{10} (DFS * DGM) + \beta_{11} (PBT * DGM) + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

FIS = Financial Sustainability, DOD = Degree of decentralisation, BBT = Benchmark Based Target, APS = Adaptive Planning System, DFS = Dynamic Funding System, PBI = Performance Based Incentives, and DGM = Digital Maturity. $\beta_0 - \beta_5$ represent the regression coefficient; $\beta_6 - \beta_{11}$ represent the moderating effects coefficients, while ϵ represents the error term. According to Appah (2020), the interpretation of correlation (r) parameters is 0.8 – 1.0 = very strong relationship, 0.6 – 0.79 = strong relationship, 0.4 – 0.59 = moderate relationship, 0.2 – 0.39 = weak relationship; and 0.0 – 0.19 = very weak

or no relationship. The study utilised a 5% level of significance; hence we conclude that the coefficient is significantly different from zero at the 5% level if the p-values is less than or equal to 0.05. If it is greater than 0.05 then we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the coefficient is zero at our 5% significance level.

Data Presentation

The primary data was collected from respondents using the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed and later retrieved by the respondents. The primary data collected was then subjected to analysis. In testing the hypotheses of the study, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression was used. From the sample 385 copies of the questionnaire were distributed.

Table 1: Internal Consistency Reliability

Construct	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Interpretation
Financial Sustainability (FIS)	5	0.72	Acceptable reliability
Degree of Decentralisation (DOD)	5	0.76	Acceptable reliability
Benchmark Based Target (BBT)	5	0.78	Acceptable reliability
Adoptive Planning System (APS)	5	0.72	Acceptable reliability
Dynamic Funding System (DFS)	5	0.74	Acceptable reliability
Performance-Based Incentives (PBI)	5	0.78	Acceptable reliability

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Digital Maturity (DGM)	5	0.74	Acceptable reliability
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Source: Authors’ Calculation (2026)

Table 1 shows the internal consistency reliability using Cronbach’s Alpha model. The analysis of the constructs used in the questionnaire design shows that all items had a score of above 0.70, showing that the instrument suggested both good and acceptable reliability for primary data collection for this study.

Table 2 Questionnaire Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Number Retrieved	382	68.2	68.2	62.2
Number not retrieved	135	24.1	24.1	92.3
Number not properly filed	43	7.7	7.7	100.0
Total	560	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows the distribution and collection of questionnaires sent to the respondents. It was shown that 560 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, representing 100%. 382 questionnaires representing 68.2% were correctly filled and successfully retrieved from

the respondents; however, 135 questionnaires representing 24.1% were not retrieved, and 43 questionnaires representing 7.7% were not properly filed. Therefore, the analysis was performed using the 382 questionnaires retrieved from respondents.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	258	67.5	67.5	67.5
Female	124	32.5	32.5	100.0
Total	382	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows the gender of respondents in the sample of the study. 67.5%, which translates to two hundred and fifty-eight (258) respondents,

are male, while 32.5%, which translates to one hundred and twenty-four (124) respondents, are female.

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Table 4: Age Range

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18 – 25 years	48	12.6	12.6	12.6
26 – 35 years	102	26.7	26.7	39.3
36 – 45 years	128	33.5	33.5	72.8
46 – 55 years	90	23.6	23.6	96.4
56 and above years	14	3.6	3.6	100.0
Total	382	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows the age range of respondents. It was shown that 48 respondents representing 12.6% are between the age brackets of 18 – 25 years, 102 respondents representing 26.7% are between the age bracket of 26 – 35 years, 128 respondents representing 33.5% are between

the age bracket of 36 – 45 years, 90 respondents representing 23.6% are between the age bracket of 46 – 55 years, 14 respondents representing 3.6% are between the age bracket of 56 and above years.

Table 5 Educational Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid OND/HND	77	20.2	20.2	20.2
Bachelor’s Degree	98	25.7	25.7	45.9
Masters Degree	110	28.8	28.8	74.7
Doctorate Degree	10	2.6	2.6	77.3
Professional Certification	87	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	382	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 presents the educational qualifications of respondents. 77 respondents (20.3%) hold a OND/HND degree, while 98 (25.7%) hold a

bachelor’s degree. 110 (28.8%), hold a master’s degree. Those with a PhD or other professional qualifications were 10 (2.6%), and finally, 87

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(22.7%) hold a Professional Certification. The cumulative percentage indicates the progressive accumulation of respondents across different educational levels, reaching 100% for all

categories combined. This distribution offers insights into the educational backgrounds of the study sample.

Table 6: Job Title/Role

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Budget Analyst	125	32.7	32.7	32.7
Budget Officer	68	17.8	17.8	50.5
Corporate Planning Manager	72	18.8	18.8	69.3
Cost Control Manager	87	22.8	22.8	92.1
Chief Financial Officer	30	7.9	7.9	100.0
Total	382	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 shows the Job Title/Role of respondents. It was shown that 125 respondents representing 32.7% are Budget Officers, 68 respondents representing 17.8% are Budget Officers, 72 respondents representing 18.8% are

Corporate Planning Managers, 87 respondents representing 22.8% are Cost Control Managers, and 30 respondents representing 7.9% are Chief Financial Officers.

Table 7: Years of Professional Service

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Less than 1 year	22	5.8	5.8	5.8
1 – 5 years	62	16.2	16.2	22.0
6 – 10 years	110	28.8	28.8	50.8
11 – 15 years	108	28.3	28.3	79.1
over 15 years	80	20.9	20.9	100.0
Total	382	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 shows the Years of Professional Service of respondents. It was shown that 22

respondents representing 5.8% have worked for less than 1 year, 62 respondents representing

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16.2% have worked for 1 – 5 years, 110 respondents representing 28.8% have worked for 6 – 10 years, 108 respondents representing

28.3% have worked for 11 – 15 years, and finally, 80 respondents representing 20.9% have worked for over 15 years.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Degree of Decentralisation

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	Decision-making authority is delegated to lower levels of the organization	382	1.00	5.00	3.261	1.257
2	Employees and teams can make operational decisions without excessive top management approval	382	1.00	5.00	3.392	1.231
3	Resources are allocated flexibly based on current business needs rather than fixed annual budgets	382	1.00	5.00	3.523	1.328
4	Managers are evaluated more on overall performance outcomes than on strict budget compliance	382	1.00	5.00	3.582	1.483
5	Teams are encouraged to respond quickly and independently to changing business conditions.	382	1.00	5.00	3.436	1.382
Valid N (listwise)		382			3.439	1.336

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 8 depict the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the degree of centralisation in the beyond budgeting variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on degree of centralisation in the beyond budgeting. Notwithstanding, all the items mean above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.439; Std. D =1.336**) respectively.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Benchmark-Based Target

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
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1	Performance targets in this organization are based on external benchmarks rather than fixed internal budgets	382	1.00	5.00	3.348	1.243
2	Managers compare performance against competitors or industry standards when setting targets	382	1.00	5.00	3.153	1.514
3	Targets are adjusted continuously in response to market conditions and benchmarking information	382	1.00	5.00	3.148	1.326
4	Performance evaluation emphasises relative improvement compared to peers or best practices	382	1.00	5.00	3.274	1.284
5	Employees are encouraged to achieve targets that reflect competitive or market realities rather than predetermined budget figures.	382	1.00	5.00	3.183	1.238
Valid N (listwise)		382			3.221	1.321

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 9 depict the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the benchmark-based target of the beyond budgeting variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on the benchmark-based target of the beyond budgeting. Notwithstanding, all the items mean above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.221; Std. D =1.321**), respectively.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics of the Adoptive Planning System

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	Planning processes in this organization are continuously updated to reflect changing business conditions	382	1.00	5.00	3.124	1.423

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2	The organization uses rolling forecasts instead of relying solely on fixed annual plans	382	1.00	5.00	2.748	1.316
3	Managers can revise plans quickly in response to environmental or market changes	382	1.00	5.00	2.847	1.325
4	Planning activities involves regular review and adjustment of organisational priorities	382	1.00	5.00	2.638	1.251
5	Operational plans are flexible enough to support rapid decision-making and change.	382	1.00	5.00	3.127	1.241
Valid N (listwise)		382			2.897	1.311

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 9 present the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the adoptive planning system of beyond budgeting variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on the adoptive planning system of beyond budgeting. Notwithstanding, all the items mean above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =2.897; Std. D =1.311**), respectively.

Table 11: Descriptive Statistics of the Dynamic Funding System

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	Resources are allocated according to current organizational needs rather than fixed annual budgets.	382	1.00	5.00	3.156	1.352
2	Managers can obtain additional funding when new opportunities or challenges arise	382	1.00	5.00	2.335	1.426
3	Funding decisions in this organization are flexible and responsive to changing	382	1.00	5.00		

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	conditions				2.972	1.312
4	Departments are allowed to reallocate resources without lengthy approval procedures	382	1.00	5.00	3.473	1.284
5	Financial resources are distributed based on strategic priorities and performance needs.	382	1.00	5.00	3.583	1.267
Valid N (listwise)		302			3.104	1.328

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 11 depict the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the dynamic funding system of beyond budgeting variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to

determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on the dynamic funding system of beyond budgeting. Notwithstanding, all the items mean above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.104; Std. D =1.328**), respectively.

Table 12: Descriptive Statistics of Performance-Based Incentives

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Ma x	Mean	Std. D
1	Employee rewards are linked to overall performance outcomes rather than strict budget achievement	382	1.00	5.00	3.432	1.226
2	Performance incentives encourage continuous improvement and value creation.	382	1.00	5.00	3.253	1.248
3	Employees are rewarded based on relative performance compared to benchmarks or peers.	382	1.00	5.00	3.267	1.365
4	The organization uses performance measures that support teamwork and long-term success	382	1.00	5.00	3.325	1.284

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5	Incentive systems are flexible enough to reflect changing organizational priorities and conditions.	382	1.00	5.00	3.358	1.382
Valid N (listwise)		382			3.327	1.301

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 12 depicted the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the performance-based incentives of the beyond budgeting variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a fixed-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on the performance-based incentives. Notwithstanding, all the items mean above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean = 3.327; Std. D = 1.301**), respectively.

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics of Digital Maturity

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	My organization uses digital technologies to support real-time decision-making	382	1.00	5.00	3.423	1.342
2	Managers in my organization use data analytics to support planning and forecasting activities	382	1.00	5.00	3.328	1.406
3	Digital systems enable continuous performance monitoring and reporting	382	1.00	5.00	3.128	1.312
4	Technology supports flexible and adaptive planning processes within my organization	382	1.00	5.00	2.563	1.252
5	Digital tools facilitate decentralized decision-making across the organizational levels in my firm	382	1.00	5.00	2.842	1.342
Valid N (listwise)		382			3.057	1.331

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 13 present the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation

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responses on the digital maturity variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a fixed-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to determine the overall mean and

standard deviation responses on digital maturity. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.057; Std. D =1.331**) respectively.

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics of Financial Sustainability

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	My firm generates sufficient and stable financial resources to support its long-term operations	382	1.00	5.00	3.431	1.246
2	My firm maintains financial resilience against economic shocks or unexpected changes	382	1.00	5.00	3.253	1.315
3	Revenue streams are diversified to reduce financial risk	382	1.00	5.00	3.262	1.312
4	My firm effectively balances short-term financial performance with long term value creation	382	1.00	5.00	3.352	1.274
5	Financial planning supports long-term firm viability rather than short-term budget targets.	382	1.00	5.00	3.416	1.248
Valid N (listwise)		382			3.343	1.279

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in Table 14 show the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on the financial sustainability variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled above, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items

were calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on financial sustainability. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.343; Std. D =1.279**), respectively.

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Table 15: Results of Correlation Matrix

	FIS	DOD	BBT	APS	DFS	PBI	DGM
FIS Pearson Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	1 .000 382						
DOD Pearson Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	.628** .000 382	1 .000 382					
BBT Pearson Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	.664** .000 382	.624** .000 382	1 .000 382				
APS Pearson Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	.684** .000 382	.642** .000 382	.626** .000 382	1 .000 382			
DFS Pearson Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	.684** .000 382	.624** .000 382	.648** .000 382	.642** .000 382	1 .000 382		

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PBI	Pearson Correlation						1	
	Significant (2-tailed)	.628**	.646**	.624**	.682**	.626**	.000	
	N	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.382	
		382	382	382	382	382		
DGM	Pearson Correlation							1
	Significant (2-tailed)	.642**	.684**	.626**	.664**	.624**	.682**	.000
	N	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.382
		382	382	382	382	382	382	

Source: Authors’ Computation Via SPSS (2026)

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) analysis shows the moderating role of digital maturity on the relationship between beyond-budgeting practices and sustainable organizational growth of listed firms in Nigeria. Table 15 shows a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.628$, $P = 0.00$) between degree of decentralization (DOD) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria, a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.664$, $P = 0.000$) between benchmark-based target (BBT) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria, a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.684$, $P = 0.000$) between adoptive planning system Table 16: Multiple Regression Analysis Model One
Dependent Variable: FIS
Method: Least Squares

(APS) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria, a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.684$, $P = 0.000$) between dynamic funding system (DFS) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria, a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.628$, $P = 0.000$) between human capacity and performance based incentives (PBI) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria and a strong and positive ($r = 0.684$, $p = 0.000$) relationship between digital maturity (DGM) and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The findings therefore suggested a strong and positive relationship between beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria.

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Date: 05/17/26 Time: 18:22

Sample(adjusted): 1 382

Included observations: 382 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
DOD	0.285935	0.095662	2.989017	0.0256
BBT	0.249495	0.106627	2.339885	0.0342
APS	0.216547	0.102573	2.111150	0.0404
DFS	0.273341	0.123184	2.218965	0.0384
PBI	0.234756	0.112637	2.126453	0.0326
R-squared	0.482826	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.428439	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.888766	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1226.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803
Log likelihood	-376.3441	F-statistic		5.567008
Durbin-Watson stat	2.16401	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000100

Source: e-view output

Table 16 shows the multiple regression analysis of the relationship between beyond budgeting practice and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The finding revealed a positive and statistically significant (0.0256 < 0.05) relationship between the degree of decentralization (DOD) of beyond budgeting practices and the financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant (0.0342 < 0.05) relationship between benchmark-based target (BBT) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant

(0.0401 < 0.05) relationship between the adoptive planning system (APS) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant (0.0384 < 0.05) relationship between the dynamic funding system (DFS) of beyond budgeting practices and the financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant (0.0326 < 0.05) relationship between performance-based incentives (PBI) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. Hence, there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between beyond budgeting practice and the

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financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The R² (coefficient of determination) of 0.482826 and adjusted R² of 0.4284393 show that the variables combined determine about 48% and 43% of the beyond budgeting practice and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability

show that the regression equation is well formulated, explaining that the relationship between the variables combined affects the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria is statistically significant (F-stat = 5.567008; F-prob. = 0.000100).

Table 17: Multiple Regression Analysis Model Two

Dependent Variable: FIS

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/17/26 Time: 19:34

Sample(adjusted): 1 382

Included observations: 382 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	1.256856	2.606061	0.0358
DOD	0.255935	0.085662	2.987731	0.0246
BBT	0.294582	0.107658	2.736276	0.0291
APS	0.272651	0.124582	2.188526	0.0354
DFS	0.275632	0.116235	2.371334	0.0325
PBI	0.282156	0.118964	2.371776	0.0342
DGM	0.268748	0.125242	2.145829	0.0412
DOD*DGM	0.287452	0.113568	2.531100	0.0346
BBT*DGM	0.423514	0.182347	2.322572	0.0354
APS*DGM	0.367474	0.153628	2.391972	0.0343
DFS*DGM	0.364225	0.154284	2.360744	0.0342
PBI*DGM	0.336426	0.142358	2.363239	0.0425
R-squared	0.742385	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.687462	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.718266	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1234.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803

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Log likelihood	-3126.3441	F-statistic	5.837465
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Durbin-Watson stat	2.364372	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000100
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Source: e-view output

Table 16 shows the multiple regression analysis of the moderating effects of digital maturity on the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The finding revealed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0246 < 0.05$) relationship between the degree of decentralization (DOD) of beyond budgeting practices and the financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0291 < 0.05$) relationship between benchmark-based target (BBT) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0354 < 0.05$) relationship between the adoptive planning system (APS) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0325 < 0.05$) relationship between the dynamic funding system (DFS) of beyond budgeting practices and the financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0342 < 0.05$) relationship between performance-based incentives (PBI) of beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The moderator variable of digital maturity (DGM) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0412 <$

0.05) relationship on financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The interaction between the moderator variable of the digital maturity (DGM) and the independent variable of degree of decentralization (DOD) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0346 < 0.05$) relationship on financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The interaction between the moderator variable of digital maturity (DGM) and the independent variable of benchmark-based target (BBT) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0354 < 0.05$) relationship on financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The interaction between the moderator variable of digital maturity (DGM) and the independent variable of adoptive planning system (APS) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0354 < 0.05$) relationship on financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The interaction between the moderator variable of digital maturity (DGM) and the independent variable of dynamic funding system (DFS) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0342 < 0.05$) relationship on financial sustainability (FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. The interaction between the moderator variable of digital maturity (DGM) and the independent variable of performance-based incentives (PBI) showed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0342 < 0.05$) relationship on financial sustainability

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(FIS) of listed firms in Nigeria. Accordingly, the finding suggested a positive and statistically significant moderating relationship between digital maturity on the beyond budgeting practices and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The R^2 (coefficient of determination) of 0.742385 and adjusted R^2 of 0.687462 show that the variables combined determine about 74% and 68% of the beyond budgeting practice and the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability show that the regression equation is well formulated, explaining that the relationship between the variables combined affects the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria is statistically significant (F-stat = 5.567008; F-prob. = 0.000100).

Discussion of Findings

Degree of decentralization (DOD) and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The result revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between degree of decentralization and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. This suggests that firms that delegate operational and strategic decision-making authority are more capable of responding effectively to environmental uncertainty, market volatility, and competitive pressures. The finding supports contingency theory, which posits that organizational effectiveness depends on the alignment between organizational structure and environmental conditions. Prior empirical evidence show that effective

governance structures significantly enhance sustainability and financial performance among Nigerian firms. Olaoye et al (2025) study found that stronger corporate governance mechanisms positively influence sustainability reporting quality and financial performance. Additionally, study conducted by Oyerogba et al (2024) indicates that governance reforms and improved organizational flexibility contribute to financial resilience and sustainable corporate outcomes. Therefore, the study implies that organizational flexibility, distributed decision-making, and adaptive governance structures constitute critical drivers of long-term corporate resilience. The result reinforces the argument that in emerging and institutionally volatile economies, decentralization enhances strategic responsiveness, operational efficiency, innovation capacity, and stakeholder integration, thereby improving financial sustainability.

Benchmark-Based Target and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The result showed a positive and statistically significant relationship between benchmark-based targets and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. This suggests that benchmark-based targets enhance strategic control, operational efficiency, and accountability, thereby improving long-term financial resilience among listed firms in Nigeria. The result also aligns with the contingency theory, which argues that organizational effectiveness depends on adopting appropriate management systems that

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fit environmental conditions. Prior empirical evidence has shown that governance and performance measurement systems significantly enhance financial performance and sustainability outcomes among Nigerian firms (Lawal et al., 2022; Oyerogba et al., 2024). These studies reinforce the argument that benchmark-oriented management systems contribute significantly to financial sustainability. This result reinforces the argument that benchmark based targets are not merely administrative tools but strategic determinants of financial sustainability. Therefore, firms that institutionalize benchmark-driven performance management are likely to improve cost control, profitability, liquidity management, and long-term shareholder value.

Adoptive Planning System (APS) and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The finding indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between adoptive planning and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The finding suggests that firms that employ flexible and responsive planning mechanisms are more likely to achieve sustainable financial performance. APS enable firms to continuously adjust strategic objectives, operational processes, and resource allocations in response to changing environmental conditions. This finding aligns with strategic management literature emphasizing the relevance of strategic flexibility and continuous planning in attaining firm sustainability. Prior empirical evidence

supports the link between APS and FIS. Lawal et al (2022) found that organizational efficiency and governance mechanisms positively influence financial performance among Nigerian firms. Likewise, Oyerogba et al (2024) reported that effective governance and strategic management frameworks improve sustainability outcomes and organizational accountability. The evidence from China also supports the relationship between adaptive systems and financial sustainability. Liu and Qi (2024) found that digital transformation and adaptive organizational systems significantly improve financial resilience among Chinese listed firms by reducing operational risks and improving governance structure. Additionally, Yang et al. (2024) study showed that digitalization and flexible operational systems positively affect financial performance through enhanced organizational adaptability network capabilities. Moreover, Phan et al. (2024) reported that adaptive management control systems positively influence organizational resilience and performance. The statistically significant of the connection indicates that adaptive planning systems constitute a critical strategic determinant of financial sustainability among Nigerian listed firms.

Dynamic Funding System and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The hypothesis test suggested a positive and statistically significant relationship between dynamic funding system and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. This finding suggests that firms that

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adopt flexible and adaptive financing mechanisms are more likely to achieve long-term financial stability and resilience. DFS enable firms to adapt financing decisions to environmental changes, thereby improving financial sustainability. Recent empirical evidence supports the relationship between dynamic funding system and financial sustainability. Zhou and Li (2024) found that financial technology significantly accelerates firm adjustment toward target capital structures by reducing financing constraints and improving information transparency. Similarly, Khan et al (2024) reported that dynamic financing decisions significantly influence sustainable capital structures among listed firms GCC countries, emphasizing that flexible financing systems improve firms' stability and growth. Alhajjeh and Besim (2024) revealed that firms adopting adaptive financing strategies during periods of crisis improved financial resilience by reducing excessive debt exposure and improving risk management practices. Ju (2024) in Korean listed firms, found that dynamic capital structure adjustments contribute significantly to sustainable corporate growth and financial performance. Consequently, the finding indicates that dynamic funding systems are strategic determinants of financial sustainability rather than merely operational financing tool.

Performance Based Incentives and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The finding showed a positive and statistically significant

relationship between performance-based incentives and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The finding suggest that incentive-aligned compensation systems are vital governance mechanism for enhancing long-term corporate financial resilience. Empirical evidence in developed and emerging markets consistently demonstrate that performance-based pay relates to improved firm performance, higher productivity and strong financial returns. Adu et al. (2022) study demonstrates that incentive-based compensation enhances not only financial outcomes but also broader sustainability performance, including risk management and long-term strategic orientation. Noja et al (2020) further show that executive financial incentives positively influence firm performance and sustainability outcomes in European firms. Therefore, these studies suggest that performance-based incentives improve operational efficiency, and strategic alignment, thereby enhancing financial sustainability. However, the effectiveness of incentive systems depends on careful design to avoid unintended consequences such as short-termism or earnings manipulation.

Digital Maturity and Financial Sustainability (FIS): The hypothesis test suggested a positive and statistically significant relationship between digital maturity and financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The finding suggests that firms with higher levels of digital integration achieve stronger

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long-term financial resilience, profitability, stability, and efficient resource allocation. Empirical evidence revealed that digital transformation significantly improves firm performance and sustainability outcomes by enhancing innovation capacity, operational efficiency, and strategic agility (Billi & Bernando, 2025; Stephenson et al., 2025). Furthermore, a panel evidence from Europe suggests that digital transformation enhances firm profitability and market valuation by improving operational efficiency and reducing transaction frictions, particularly through stronger information processing capabilities and faster decision cycles (Cittrio et al., 2024). Wan (2025) study in the U. S. revealed that higher digital transformation intensity significantly increases asset turnover and operating efficiency, which translates into improved financial performance and cash flow stability over time. Consequently, these studies converge on the conclusion that digital maturity improves financial sustainability by enhancing operational efficiency and asset productivity, improving risk management and internal control systems. Generally, the positive and statistically significant result suggests that digital maturity is a key strategic determinant of financial sustainability, particularly in uncertain macroeconomic environments.

Conclusion, Policy Implications, Limitations and Future Research

The findings of this study provide empirical evidence that beyond budgeting practices

significantly enhances the financial sustainability of listed firms in Nigeria. The results reveal that degree of decentralization, benchmark-based targets, adoptive planning systems, dynamic funding systems, and performance-based incentives each exhibit positive and statistically significant relationships with financial sustainability. These findings suggest that adaptive and flexible management practices enhance efficiency, and long-term viability in dynamic business environments. Furthermore, the study establishes that digital maturity positively and significantly moderates the relationship between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable organizational growth. This indicates that firms with stronger digital capabilities are better positioned to maximise the effectiveness of adaptive management systems and achieve superior sustainability outcomes. The study therefore concludes that firms seeking sustainable organizational growth and enduring financial sustainability should prioritize the institutionalization of decentralized governance structures, adaptive planning mechanisms, flexible funding architectures, benchmark-oriented performance systems, and digitally enabled management capabilities. Such strategic alignment is essential for enhancing competitiveness, improving organizational resilience, and ensuring sustainable value creation in increasingly uncertain and technologically driven business environments.

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The findings of this study have important policy implications for corporate managers, regulators, and policymakers in Nigeria. First, organisations should promote decentralized decision-making structure to enhance managerial flexibility, responsiveness, and operational efficiency. Second, firms should adopt benchmark-based performance systems and adaptive planning mechanisms that enable continuous evaluation and strategic adjustment in response to changing market conditions. The positive influence of dynamic funding systems further suggests the need for flexible resource allocation policies, and rapid organizational adaptation. In addition, performance-based incentive systems should be strengthened to improve employee motivation, accountability, and productivity, thereby enhancing financial sustainability. The significant moderating role of digital maturity also highlights the necessity for firms to invest in digital infrastructure, data analytics capabilities and technological innovation. Policymakers and regulatory agencies should therefore encourage digital transformation through supportive policies, capacity-building initiatives, and improved technological infrastructure. Collectively, these measures would enhance sustainable organizational growth, financial resilience, and long-term competitiveness of listed firms in Nigeria.

This study is not without limitations. First, the study focused exclusively on listed firms in Nigeria, which may limit the generalizability of

the findings to non-listed firms or organisations operating in other economic contexts. Second, the cross-sectional nature of the study restricts the ability to establish long-term causal associations among the variables. Third, the study relied primarily on questionnaire data, which may not fully capture the contextual and behavioural dynamics influencing beyond budgeting practices and organizational sustainability. Future research should therefore consider longitudinal designs to examine the long-term effects of beyond budgeting practices on organizational sustainability. Comparative studies across different industries, sectors, and countries would also provide broader insights into the applicability of the findings. In addition, future studies may incorporate qualitative or mixed method approaches to obtain deeper understanding of managerial experiences and organizational processes related with beyond budgeting practices. Future research should explore additional moderating or mediating variables such as organizational culture, innovation capability, and leadership style, which may influence the connection between beyond budgeting practices and sustainable economic growth.

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